

Taberes, a new genus of the family Tornidae (Gastropoda, Truncatelloidea) from the Pacific Ocean, with the description of 7 new species

Taberes, un nuevo género de la familia Tornidae (Gastropoda, Truncatelloidea) del Océano Pacífico, con la descripción de 7 nuevas especies

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RESUMEN

Se describen un nuevo género y 7 nuevas especies pertenecientes a la familia Tornidae (=Vitrinellidae) (Caenogastropoda: Truncatelloidea). Las especies estudiadas proceden del sudeste del Pacífico tropical en Vanuatu, Islas Salomón, Filipinas y Papúa Nueva Guinea. El nuevo género *Taberes* se ha basado en caracteres morfológicos únicos presentes en las siete nuevas especies descritas; se discute su posición sistemática y se compara con otros géneros con caracteres morfológicos similares. Cada una de las especies se ilustra mediante fotografías al microscopio electrónico de barrido, discutiendo su variabilidad específica y aportando datos sobre el hábitat, distribución geográfica y rango batimétrico.

ABSTRACT

A new genus and 7 new species belonging to the family Tornidae (=Vitrinellidae) (Caenogastropoda: Truncatelloidea) are described. The species studied are from the southeastern tropical Pacific in Vanuatu, Solomon Is., Philippines and Papua New Guinea. The new genus *Taberes* is based on unique morphological features that are present in the seven new species described; their systematic position is discussed and the new genus is compared with others genera presenting similar morphological characters. Each species is illustrated by scanning electron microscope photographs; their specific variability is discussed and information about their habitat, geographical distribution and bathymetric range is provided.

INTRODUCTION

After the examination of the “vitrinelliform” gastropods from the tropical Pacific collected mostly during the Tropical Deep-Sea Benthos and Our Planet Reviewed expeditions conducted respectively by IRD and MNHN, and MNHN and Pro-Natura International, our attention has been drawn on some groups dis-

playing unique sets of characters, leading us to describe them as new genera *Mondosus* (RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2016) and *Circuitus* (RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2017).

A further small group of species which, in view of their general appearance, could belong to the genus *Circulus* Philippi, 1836 but was finally retained as

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distinct and is the object of the present paper.

They have a depressed-turbinat, keeled and widely umbilicate shell, with a thickened outer lip and nodes on its inner part. PONDER (1994: 258) defined the genus *Circulus* as: “*vitrinellids having a spirally ridged shell with a simple non varicose aperture, ...*”. The thickening lip and the nodes on its interior part all are characters found in the described species below and absents in the species of the genus *Circulus*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The material studied in this paper originates essentially from several expeditions conducted by MNHN and Pro-Natura International (PNI) in partnership with University of Papua New Guinea (UPNG) as part of the *Our Planet Reviewed* programme (PAPUA NIUGINI 2012); by MNHN and Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (IRD) as part of the *Tropical Deep-Sea Benthos* programme (MUSORSTOM 8, SALOMON 1; see BOUCHET ET AL. 2008). Material from the Central Philippines: Panglao, Dauis, Cortes, Tagbilaran and Baclayon, and the Bohol and Sulu Seas, is also included.

The abovementioned expeditions are detailed as follows:

MUSORSTOM 8 (1994) on board R/V *Alis*, explored the Vanuatu Archipelago.

SALOMON 1 (2001) on board R/V *Alis* surveyed the central part of the Solomon Islands, from Guadalcanal to Malaita and Makira.

PAPUA NIUGINI 2012 expedition to the Madang Lagoon and the adjacent part of the Bismarck Sea, Papua New Guinea.

Illustrations for all the studied species were prepared using a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) Quanta 200 and EVO LS15. Measurements of the teleoconch, the maximum height (H) and maximum diameter (D) are based on the scale bar of the SEM micrographs.

The protoconch was measured by VERDUIN'S (1976) method in which a nucleus is considered at the beginning of the spire.

Abbreviations:

MNHN Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris

D maximum diameter of the shell, measured perpendicular to the axis of coiling

H total height of the shell

stn station

s clearly empty shells

(Right page) Figure 1. All the species of *Tuberes* n. gen. shown in two views, together for comparison (all MNHN). A, B: *T. solomonensis* n. sp., holotype, diameter 1.67 mm, Solomon Islands, stn DW1787, 316-344 m. C, D: *T. minutuber* n. sp., holotype, diameter 2.7 mm, Solomon Islands, stn DW1762, 396-411 m. E, F: *T. minutuber* n. sp., paratype, diameter 2.34 mm, Solomon Islands, stn DW1769, 200-303 m. G, H: *T. vanuatuensis* n. sp., holotype, diameter 2.49 mm, Vanuatu, stn DW1101, 205-210 m. I, J: *T. papuensis* n. sp., holotype, diameter 2.17 mm, Papua New Guinea, stn PD10, 15-28 m. K, L: *T. philippinensis* n. sp., paratype, diameter 2.06 mm, Philippines, stn T18, 80-100 m. M, N: *T. marianae* n. sp., holotype, diameter 2.3 mm, Philippines, 137-163 m. P, Q: *T. postremus* n. sp., holotype, diameter 2.43 mm, Philippines, 145-163 m. R, S: *T. postremus* n. sp., paratype, diameter 2.06 mm, Philippines, stn CP2362, 679-740 m.

(Página derecha) Figura 1. Todas las especies de *Tuberes* n. gen. figuradas en dos vistas, juntas para la comparación (todos en MNHN). A, B: *T. solomonensis* n. sp., holotipo, diámetro 1,67 mm, Islas Salomón, stn DW1787, 316-344 m. C, D: *T. minutuber* n. sp., holotipo, diámetro 2,7 mm, Islas Salomón, stn DW1762, 396-411 m. E, F: *T. minutuber* n. sp., paratipo, diámetro 2,34 mm, Islas Salomón, stn DW1769, 200-303 m. G, H: *T. vanuatuensis* n. sp., holotipo, diámetro 2,49 mm, Vanuatu, stn DW1101, 205-210 m. I, J: *T. papuensis* n. sp., holotipo, diámetro 2,17 mm, Papua Nueva Guinea, stn PD10, 15-28 m. K, L: *T. philippinensis* n. sp., paratipo, diámetro 2,06 mm, Filipinas, 80-100 m. M, N: *T. marianae* n. sp., holotipo, diámetro 2,3 mm, Filipinas, 137-163 m. P, Q: *T. postremus* n. sp., holotipo, diámetro 2,43 mm, Filipinas, 145-163 m. R-S: *T. postremus* n. sp., paratipo, diámetro 2,06 mm, Filipinas, stn CP2362, 679-740 m.

SYSTEMATIC PART

Superfamily TRUNCATELLOIDEA Gray, 1840

Family TORNIDAE Sacco, 1896

Subfamily VITRINELLINAE Bush, 1897

Tuberes n. gen.

Type species: *Tuberes solomonensis* n. sp.

Etymology: The genus name *Tuberes* is the plural nominative of the Latin word *tuber*, *is*, which means “protuberances, prominences, nodes” alluding the constant presence of numerous regular nodes on the outer lip.

Description: Shell depressed-turbini-form, with a low to very low spire; protoconch slightly elevated with respect to the first teleoconch whorl, usually multispiral; teleoconch whorls with keeled spiral cords, 7-9 on the last whorl; umbilicus widely opened with 0-2 cords inside. Axial riblets present on the last part of the shell and continued inside the umbilicus. Micro granules present in areas close to the suture. Aperture circular, with the outer lip not thickened externally but with a thick edge, with

very marked, elevated and rounded nodes on the inner rim.

Remarks: The shells included in this genus are rather similar, all sharing the main character that is the presence of strong nodes on a rounded peristome and of keeled cords, usually narrowing at their termination, with concave interspaces. For an overview, Figure 1 shows all the species here assigned to this genus in a similar position. The tubercles or nodes on the outer lip are highly diagnostic.

Tuberes solomonensis n. sp. (Figures 1A-B, 2A-D)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 1A-B, 2A-C), MNHN IM-2000-33132.

Material examined: Solomon Islands, SALOMON 1: 1 s, Solomon Islands, stn DW1787, 9°19'S-160°20'E, 316-344 m.

Type locality: Solomon Islands, 9°19'S-160°20'E, 316-344 m [SALOMON 1: stn DW1787].

Etymology: The specific name refers to the archipelago where the species was collected.

Description: Shell, turbiniiform, with a moderately depressed profile; protoconch slightly elevated with respect to the teleoconch, with 2.25 whorls, about 550 μm in diameter, and a nucleus of about 50 μm ; its surface is smooth and the width of the whorls increases slowly. Teleoconch with 1.5 whorl, with keeled spiral cords, 7 on the last whorl, narrow on their upper part, separated by a concave groove; umbilicus widely open with 3 additional cords inside, more closely packed than the others, rounded, with small, uniformly separated axial riblets inside the umbilicus. Micro granules were not observed in the areas close to the suture. Aperture circular, col-

umella thickened and slightly reflected; outer lip with the external edge marked with the end of the spiral cords, on its inner side with nine strongly marked, elevated and rounded nodes.

Dimensions: the holotype has 1.67 mm in diameter and 1.19 mm in height.

Habitat: Bathyal species dredged at 316-344 m.

Distribution: Only known from Solomon Islands.

Remarks: *Tuberes solomonensis* n. sp. can be differentiated from *T. minituber*, *T. vanuatuensis*, *T. philippinensis*, *T. marianae* and *T. postremus* by its more elevated profile. The most similar species, having a similar elevated spire is *T. papuensis*, from which

Figure 2. *Tuberes solomonensis* n. sp. A-C: holotype (MNHN), diameter 1.67 mm, Solomon Is. stn DW1787, 316-344 m; D: protoconch.

Figura 2. *Tuberes solomonensis* n. sp. A-C: holotipo (MNHN), diámetro 1,67 mm, Islas Salomón, stn DW1787, 316-344 m; D: protoconcha.

is differentiated by being smaller, having a wider protoconch with $\frac{1}{4}$ whorl more, and having the axial sculpture in the base and inside the umbilicus less conspicu-

ous. Also, in the latter species, the nodules are placed on the middle part of the rim of the outer lip, not somewhat inwards as in *T. solomonensis* n. sp.

Tuberes minituber n. sp. (Figures 1C-D, 3A-F, 4A-E)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 1C-D, 3A-C), MNHN IM-2000-33133, and paratype (Fig. 4A-C), MNHN IM-2000-33134.

Material examined: Solomon Islands, SALOMON 1: 1 s, Solomon Islands, stn DW1762, 8°40'S-160°04'E, 396-411 m (holotype); 1 s, Solomon Islands, stn DW1769, 8°20'S-160°41'E, 290-303 m (paratype).

Type locality: Solomon Islands, 8°40'S-160°04'E, 396-411 m [SALOMON 1: stn DW1762].

Etymology: The specific name derives from the Latin adverb "*minime*" which means "smaller" and "*tuber*", referring to the nodes in the aperture, which are smaller than in other species.

Description: Shell depressed-turbini-form, with a very low spire; protoconch slightly elevated with respect to the

teleoconch, with 2.5 whorls, about 550 μm in diameter, and a nucleus of about 50 μm ; its surface is smooth and the

Figure 3. *Tuberes minituber* n. sp. A-C: holotype (MNHN), diameter 2.7 mm, stn DW1762, Solomon Is.; D: protoconch; E, F: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 3. *Tuberes minituber* n. sp. A-C: *holotipo* (MNHN), diámetro 2,7 mm, stn DW1762, Islas Salomón; D: *protoconcha*; E, F: *microescultura y detalle*.

width of the whorls increases slowly. Teleoconch with two whorls and keeled spiral cords, the first one to appear being larger situated in the middle of the spire whorl, an another one near the suture; an additional cord appears just

above the suture and is continued on the periphery of the last whorl. The larger cord is narrow on its crest, with a concave surface on both sides; on the last whorl, there are 9 cords, the lower two within the umbilicus. At the end of

Figure 4. *Tuberes minituber* n. sp. A-C: paratype (MNHN), diameter 2.34 mm, stn DW1769, Solomon Is.; D: protoconch; E: microsculpture.

Figura 4. *Tuberes minituber* n. sp. A-C: paratipo (MNHN), diámetro 2,34 mm, stn DW1769, Islas Salomón; D: protoconcha; E: microescultura.

the last whorl, two more cords appear between the previous ones and also, numerous, evenly spaced small axial riblets cover this area, penetrating into the umbilicus. Micro granules were observed in the areas close to the suture (Figs. 3F-E). Aperture circular, peristome continuous; columella thickened and slightly reflected; outer lip with the external edge marked with the end of the spiral cords, on its inner side with

10-11 very scarcely elevated, rounded nodes, sometimes forming pairs.

Dimensions: The holotype is 2.7 mm in diameter and 1.53 mm in height.

Habitat: Bathyal species dredged at 290-411 m.

Distribution: Only known in the Solomon archipelago.

Remarks: *Tuberes minituber* n. sp. differs with *T. solomonensis* n. sp. in being larger and more depressed; the

spiral ribs do not penetrate so deeply into the umbilicus and the nodes on the peristome are smaller and irregularly disposed, sometimes in pairs.

In some shells, the axial riblets were not observed at the end of the spire, perhaps because growth could be incomplete.

Tuberes vanuatuensis n. sp. (Figures 1G-H, 5A-D)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 1G-H, 5A-C), MNHN IM-2000-33135, and 9 paratypes, MNHN IM-2000-33136.

Type locality: Vanuatu, 15°04'S-167°08'E, 205-210 m [MUSORSTOM 8: stn DW1101].

Material examined: Vanuatu: 10 s (type material).

Etymology: The specific name refers to the island where the species was collected.

Description: Shell depressed-turbini-form, with a very low spire; protoconch slightly elevated with respect to the teleoconch, with 2.2 whorls, about 510 μm in diameter, and a nucleus of about 70 μm ; its surface is smooth and the width of the whorls increases slowly. Teleoconch with two whorls, with spiral carinae, the first of them being the largest and situated in the middle of the spire whorls, and another one is near the suture; an additional cord appears just above the suture and is continued just above the periphery of the last whorl. The largest cords are narrow on their crest, with a concave surface on both sides; on the last whorl, there are 9 cords, the lower one placed on the edge of the umbilicus, inside which there are several spiral cordlets. In the final part of the last whorl, two additional cords appear between the former ones and also, numerous small axial riblets uniformly separated cover this area, only in the adapical part. No micro granules were observed in areas close to the

suture. Aperture circular, peristome continuous; columella simple, not thickened; outer lip with the external border marked by the end of the spiral cords, on its inner side with 12-13 hardly elevated, rounded nodules, sometimes forming pairs, clearly extending towards inside the aperture.

Dimensions: Holotype 2.49 mm in diameter and 1.56 mm in height.

Habitat: Bathyal species dredged at 205-210 m.

Distribution: Only known from Vanuatu.

Remarks: *Tuberes solomonensis* n. sp. is smaller, more elevated in profile, with larger nodes on the peristome, where they are uniformly distributed, and in lower number.

Tuberes minutuber n. sp. has a wider protoconch, with 1/4 whorl more; the umbilical wall has axial sculpture; there are numerous micro granules on the surface close to the suture; the apertural nodes are smaller and do not extend at all towards inside.

Tuberes papuensis n. sp. (Figures 1I-J, 6A-F)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 1I-J, 6A-D), MNHN IM-2000-33137.

Material examined: Papua New Guinea, Madang Lagoon, PAPUA NIUGINI: 1 s, W Kranket Island, stn PD10, 5°11.5'S-145°48.5'E, 16-28 m; 1 s, Sek Island, stn PD26, 5°5.55'S-145°49.5'E, 18-22 m.

Type locality: Papua New Guinea, Madang Lagoon, W Kranket Island, 5°11.5'S-145°48.5'E, 16-28 m [PAPUA NIUGINI: stn PD10].

Etymology: The specific name is from the gentile name "papu".

Description: Shell turbini-form, with a moderately depressed profile; protoconch slightly elevated with respect to

the teleoconch, with 2.5 whorls, about 480 μm of diameter, and a nucleus of about 50 μm ; its surface is smooth and

Figure 5. *Tuberes vanuatuensis* n. sp. A-C: holotype (MNHN), diameter 2.49 mm, stn DW1101, Vanuatu; D: protoconch.

Figura 5. *Tuberes vanuatuensis* n. sp. A-C: holotipo (MNHN), diámetro 2,49 mm, stn DW1101, Vanuatu; D: protoconcha.

the width of the whorls increases slowly. Teleoconch of a little less than two whorls, the spire whorls with 2 prominent spiral keels and a third one bordering the suture and continued at the periphery of the last whorl; spiral cords in total 10 on the last whorl, narrow on their crest, with a concave surface between them; umbilicus widely open, inside with 4 rounded cords, more closely packed than the others, and with small, evenly separated axial riblets. Micro granules were not observed in areas close to the suture. Aperture circular, peristome continuous; columella thickened and reflected; outer lip with external edge irregularly affected by the spi-

ral cords; in the parietal area a depression is present at the union of the upper part of the columella with the external part of the aperture. Edge of the outer lip with 8-9 very marked, elevated and rounded nodes situated on the middle part of the apertural rim, the lower ones attenuated.

Dimensions: The holotype is 2.17 mm in diameter and 1.45 mm in height.

Habitat: Infralittoral species collected at 18-22 m.

Distribution: Only known from the Papua New Guinea.

Remarks: *Tuberes papuensis* n. sp. is most similar to *Tuberes solomonensis* n. sp. but the latter is smaller, has a wider

Figure 6. *Tuberes papuensis* n. sp. A-D: holotype (MNHN), diameter 2.17 mm, stn PD10, Papua New Guinea; E: protoconch; F: detail of the axial sculpture of the base.

Figura 6. *Tuberes papuensis* n. sp. A-D: holotipo (MNHN), diámetro 2,17 mm, stn PD10, Papua Nueva Guinea; E: protoconcha; F: detalle de la escultura axial de la base.

protoconch, with $\frac{1}{4}$ whorl more, the axial sculpture in the base and inside the umbilicus is less conspicuous, and the nodes are situated more internally,

not so clearly in the middle of the peristome.

It is the only species collected in shallow water.

Tuberes philippinensis n. sp. (Figures 1K-L, 7A-E)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 1K-L, 7C-D), MNHN IM-2000-33138 and paratype (Figs. 7A-B), MNHN IM-2000-33139

Material examined: Philippines: 2 s, Bohol Island, Cortes, stn T18, 9°41.8'N-123°49.9' E, 80-100 m, muddy bottom with sponges (type material); 1 s, Panglao Island, off San Isidro, stn T9, 9°33.5'N-123°49.5'E, 97-120 m.

Type locality: Philippines, Bohol Islands, Cortes, 9°41.8'N-123°49.9' E, 80-100 m, muddy bottom with sponges.

Etymology: The specific name refers to the archipelago where the species was collected.

Description: Shell discoid, depressed-turbiniiform; protoconch slightly elevated with respect to the teleoconch, with 2.25 whorls, about 540 μm in diameter, and a nucleus of about 50 μm ; its surface is smooth and the width of the whorls increases slowly. Teleoconch with keeled spiral cords, only two at the beginning and 7-8 in the last whorl, the lower 1-2 being very narrow and bordering the umbilicus; at the end of the spire, larger shells have more spiral cords (up to 16, in contrast to 8 in smaller shells). Umbilicus very wide with a smooth inner surface in which very light axial riblets crossed by the two lower cords can be seen. Micro granules were not observed in areas close to the suture. Aperture circular, peristome continuous; columella with a small spur on the middle part projecting inside the umbilicus; outer lip thick, with the external edge marked with the end of the numerous spiral cords and with very 9-10 marked, elevated and rounded nodes on its internal part.

Dimensions: The holotype has 2.34 mm in diameter x 1.43 mm in height.

Habitat: Circalittoral species dredged at 80-120 m on muddy bottom with sponges.

Distribution: Only known from Philippines.

Remarks: *Tuberes philippinensis* n. sp. has the typical characters of the genus, but with some differences with the previously described species:

Tuberes solomonensis n. sp. is smaller, more elevated, the spiral cords are more numerous and several of them are inside the umbilicus, crossed here by axial riblets.

Tuberes minituber n. sp. has very different nodes on the outer lip, smaller and frequently in pairs; it has $\frac{1}{4}$ whorl more of protoconch and a microsculpture near the suture.

Tuberes vanuatuensis n. sp. has a slightly smaller protoconch, the nodes of the aperture are in a more internal position and extend towards the inside.

Tuberes papuensis n. sp. has a more elevated shell, a smaller protoconch, the lower spiral cords are inside the umbilicus, where axial riblets are also present.

Tuberes marianae n. sp. (Figures 1M-N, 8A-F)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 1M-N, 8A-C), MNHN IM-2000-33140.

Material examined: Only the type specimen.

Type locality: Philippines, Bohol Sea, Maribojoc Bay, 9°43.3'N-123°47.6'E, 121-137 m.

Etymology: The specific name is after Mariana Landin, Professor of the Department of Pharmacology, Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Technology in the University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain, for her cooperation.

Description: Shell depressed-turbiniiform; protoconch slightly elevated with respect to the teleoconch, with 2.25 whorls, about 500 μm of diameter, and a nucleus of about 50 μm ; its surface is smooth and

the width of the whorls increases slowly. Teleoconch with rather depressed spiral cords, only two at the beginning and 7 in the last whorl, the lowest very fine and widely separated from the previous one;

Figure 7. *Tuberes philippinensis* n. sp. A, B: paratype (MNHN), diameter 2.08 mm, Philippines, Bohol, 80-100 m; C, D: holotype (MNHN), diameter 2.34 mm, same locality. E: protoconch. *Figura 7. Tuberes philippinensis* n. sp. A, B: paratipo (MNHN), diámetro 2,08 mm, Filipinas, Bohol, 80-100 m; C, D: holotipo (MNHN), diámetro 2,34 mm, misma localidad. E: protoconcha.

umbilicus very wide, with a wide and smooth umbilical infundibulum reaching almost till the fine lower spiral cord; at the end of the spire, one more spiral cord appears close to the suture and very light axial riblets crossing the spiral cords can also be seen. Micro granules were not observed in areas close to the suture. Aperture circular, peristome continuous; columella with a short callus projecting towards the umbilicus; outer lip with the external edge marked by the ends of the spiral cords; outer lip having 10 promi-

nent nodes on its inner side, the lowest one smaller.

Dimensions: The holotype is 2.3 mm in diameter and 1.35 mm in height.

Habitat: Circalittoral species dredged at 121-137 m.

Distribution: Only known in Philippines.

Remarks: The more depressed spiral cords, and the base without the usually sized spiral cords are the differential characters of this species *versus* to the other previously studied.

Figure 8. *Tuberes marianae* n. sp. A-C: holotype (MNHN), diameter 2.3 mm, Philippines; D: protoconch; E, F: sculpture of the end of the spire and detail.

Figura 8. *Tuberes marianae* n. sp. A-C: holotipo (MNHN), diámetro 2,3 mm, Filipinas; D: protoconcha; E, F: escultura del final de la espira y detalle.

Tuberes postremus n. sp. (Figures 1P-Q, 9A-G, 10A-F)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 1P-Q, 9A-D), MNHN IM-2000-33141 and 11 paratypes (Figs. 10A-F), MNHN IM-2000-33142.

Material examined: Philippines: 12 s, between Libaong and Pamilacan, stn T34, 9°31.3'N-123°51.4'E, 145-163 m, sand with Echinoderms (type material); 5 s, Bohol Island, W of Baclayon, stn T5, 9°35.3'N-123°52.2'E, 84-87 m, coarse muddy sand; 2 s, Panglao Island, off San Isidro, stn T10, 9°33.4'N-123°49.6'E, 117-124 m; 3 s, Panglao Island, Biking, Catarman, stn T28, 9°35.0'N-123°51.4'E, 80 m; 6 s, W Pamilacan Island, Cervera shoal, stn T36, 9°29.3'N-123°51.5'E sand on Echinoderms bed; 1 s, Panglao Island, Bolod, stn T4, 9°33.0'N-123°48.5'E, 82 m; 3 S, Bohol Island, Cortes, stn T26, 9°43.3'N-123°48.8'E, 123-135 m, mud; 1 s, Bohol Island, Maribojoc Bay, stn T11, 9°40.9'N-123°50.0'E, 78-95 m, sponges and muddy sand; 2 s, Bohol Island, Maribojoc Bay, stn T14, 9°42'N-123°49'E, 101-110 m, mud with shells; 1 s, W Pamilacan Island, Cervera shoal, stn. T39, 9°30.1'N-123°50.4'E, 100-138 m; 1 s, Bohol Sea, off Pamilacan Island, stn CP2343, 9°27.4'N-123°49.4'E, 273-356 m; 1 s, Bohol/Sulu Seas, stn CP2362, 8°56.5'N-123°32.7'E, 679-740 m.

Type locality: Philippines, between Libaong and Pamilacan, 9°31.3'N-123°51.4'E, 145-163 m, sand with echinoderms.

Etymology: The specific name derives from the Latin word *postremus* which means "the last one".

Description: Shell depressed-turbini-form; protoconch slightly elevated with respect to the teleoconch, with 2.25 whorls, about 560 μm of diameter, and a nucleus of about 70 μm ; its surface is smooth and the width of the whorls increases slowly. Teleoconch with 1.2 to 1.5 whorls with keeled spiral cords, only two at the beginning and 7 in the last whorl, the lowest one rounded. Umbilicus very wide with a wide and smooth umbilical infundibulum, limited by the lowest spiral cord; no axial riblets. Micro granules observed in areas close to the suture (Figs. 9F-G, 10E-F). Aperture circular; columella with a very short spur projecting towards the umbilicus; outer lip thick, with the outer edge marked with the end of the spiral cords, having on its inner part about 8 not very prominent nodes, somewhat irregularly disposed.

Dimensions: Holotype is 2.43 mm in diameter and 1.66 mm in height.

Habitat: Bathyal species dredged from 145 to 740 m.

Distribution: Only known from Philippines Is.

Remarks: The shells which were included in this taxon surprisingly were collected in very different depths (from 145-163 m to 679-740 m). In spite of this we did not find any morphological differences and so, we have preferred to keep them in only one taxon.

Against the other species in this study we found the following comparative differences:

Tuberes solomonensis n. sp. is smaller, more elevated, with more numerous keeled spiral cords, the lower ones extending inside the umbilical infundibulum, and with axial riblets inside the umbilicus.

Tuberes minituber n. sp. has a couple of cords inside the umbilical infundibulum as well as axial sculpture. The nodes in the peristome are very small.

Tuberes vanuatuensis n. sp. has a smaller protoconch, the teleoconch sculpture begins with two keeled spiral cords and on the first whorl a new cord appears; it has no microsculpture near the suture, and the umbilical infundibulum has small spiral cordlets.

Tuberes papuensis n. sp. has a more elevated shell, the spiral cords penetrate deeper in the umbilical infundibulum, where axial sculpture is evident; the nodes in the aperture are large and placed in the middle of the edge of the outer lip.

Tuberes philippinensis n. sp. has the columellar spur smaller, the nodes are large and regularly separated, and no micro granules were observed near the suture.

Tuberes marianae n. sp. has a smaller protoconch, the spiral cords are more depressed while the base has no spiral cords and only a very fine cordlet.

Figure 9. *Tuberes postremus* n. sp. A-D: holotype (MNHN), diameter 2.43 mm, Philippines, 145-163 m; E: protoconch; F, G: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 9. *Tuberes postremus* n. sp. A-D: holotipo (MNHN), diámetro 2,43 mm, Filipinas, 145-163 m; E: protoconcha; F, G: microescultura y detalle.

Figure 10. *Tuberes postremus* n. sp. A-C: paratype (MNHN), diameter 2.06 mm, stn CP2362, Philippines, 679-740 m; D: protoconch; E, F: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 10. *Tuberes postremus* n. sp. A-C: paratipo (MNHN), diámetro 2,06 mm, stn CP2362, Filipinas, 679-740 m; D: protoconcha; E, F: microescultura y detalle.

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